

KNOWLEDGE SOCIETY IN AZERBAIJAN AND MUSEUMS: DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS**Jafarova Nazmin***PhD on Art Study,**Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences,**Azerbaijan, Baku***Abstract**

One of the priority tasks facing us is the development of a knowledge society, a knowledge economy and its component, a creative economy, in Azerbaijan. The development of museums in the republic, the widespread use of modern technologies in the work of domestic museums, the implementation by museums of projects aimed at educating the population, providing cultural leisure and, at the same time, attracting additional financial resources – all these tasks are of particular relevance.

Along with the collection, storage, study and demonstration of museum objects, one of the areas of activity of museums is educational activities. In a period of constantly growing information flow, society needs comprehensive and accessible information. Museums are indispensable sources of such information. At this stage, it is necessary to conduct monitoring in order to find out the current state of affairs in this area, and to develop a unified concept for determining the prospects for the development of museums.

Keywords: knowledge society, knowledge economy, creative economy, Azerbaijan, culture, art, tourism, science, education, museums.

Guided by the call of the head of state to “transform oil capital into human capital”, one of the priority tasks is the development in Azerbaijan of a knowledge society, knowledge economy and its component – the creative economy. The formation of a creative economy is closely related to the development of many industries, including tourism. The productive use of tourism potential is also associated with a number of issues, including the implementation of museum activities in accordance with the requirements of the time.

We believe that the development of a knowledge society directly depends on the integration of science and education. Museums occupy a unique place in solving this problem. When considering the numerous events implemented by museums, it becomes clear that currently these temples of culture and science perform many social functions, such as collecting, studying and displaying materials about current events, participation in the process of education and upbringing, recreational, communication, informational, aesthetic, economic functions, etc. [20, p. 61].

All of the above gives grounds to assert that museums play a major role in the formation of a knowledge society. In turn, we must implement various initiatives aimed at accelerating this process, direct the activities of the country’s museums in the appropriate direction and create new museums that meet the requirements of the time.

Tourism sector and museums. Today tourism is one of the main sectors of the economy of the leading countries of the world. Therefore, the development of museum construction in the republic, the widespread use of modern technologies in museum affairs, the implementation by museums of projects aimed at educating the population, providing cultural leisure and, at the

same time, obtaining additional financial resources – all these issues become of particular relevance.

In the “Strategic Roadmap for the Development of Specialized Tourism Industry in the Republic of Azerbaijan” notes that tourism has an impact mainly on three areas. Firstly, the direct impact of tourism companies on the Gross Domestic Product increases the importance of tourism; the tourism sector acts as the main locomotive of foreign exchange earnings for countries. Secondly, the development of tourism has a positive impact on increasing employment and socio-economic development of regions. And thirdly, the creation of a strong infrastructure in the country aimed at developing tourism becomes the reason for the development of infrastructure in various regions.

In addition, the tourism sector supports initiatives in the areas of environmental sustainability, cultural heritage, protection and development of local values. A successful tourism development strategy also helps to improve the country’s image internationally, so tourism also acts as marketing tool for various countries [1, p. 8].

Scientists note that “the influence of tourism in general on specific countries, regions or tourist centers leads to the formation of three important factors in the long-term development of this area: a) environmental (ensuring environmental protection and diversity of biological resources); b) sociocultural (ensuring unity between the culture and values of the local population and the development of tourism and recreational policy); c) economic (ensuring economic productivity of development and resource management in order to meet the needs of next generations)” [7, p. 13].

Taking into account all of the above, it is necessary to emphasize that in the modern period the development of sustainable (long-term) and socially responsible tourism has acquired particular relevance.

The goal of sustainable tourism is to operate more efficiently and humanely, based on community interests and environmental opportunities. There are several factors that differentiate sustainable tourism from traditional tourism. Thus, tourism services are provided in accordance with the socio-economic and environmental capabilities of the territory, these opportunities determine the characteristics of tourism activities, tourists behave in accordance with the culture of the places they visit, respect natural objects, customs and traditions, have friendly relations with the local population on the basis of mutual respect [17].

Regarding socially responsible tourism, experts note that such tourism creates opportunities for tourists to make a real contribution to the sustainable development of the places they visit. The motto of socially responsible tourism is: "to improve the environment in which local people live and create attractive places for tourists". Through the implementation of large and small events, socially responsible tourism ensures the protection of nature, promotes the social and economic development of regions, and fosters a sense of respect for customs and traditions, historical and cultural heritage, and the environment [18, p. 13].

Thus, the creation of tourism products in accordance with the requirements of modern times will lead to the development of a creative economy in the republic. Taking into account the features of cultural and educational tourism, we note that the development of an important component of this type of tourism – museums – in accordance with the requirements of the time and the creation of new museums that meet the challenges of emerging realities will play a significant role in the formation of society and the knowledge economy. The creation of new museums is historically justified, as well as relevant and expedient both from the point of view of the development of tourism and the economy, and from the point of view of bringing the truth about Azerbaijan to the world community.

The role of museums in the integration of science and education. The role of museums in the formation of a knowledge society is not limited to their participation in the development of tourism. Speaking about the features that characterize the knowledge society, scientists note that at this time the role of science in society is increasing and, at the same time, fundamental changes are taking place in society itself, new scientific knowledge and technologies constitute the way of life of people, the essence of modern societies, space, in which people live [21, p. 65-66]. In this society, the mechanisms for applying scientific and technical knowledge are fundamentally changing, in other words, the integration of science, education and production is ensured.

The Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Science", adopted on June 14, 2016, defines the basic principles of state policy in the field of organization, management and development of scientific activity in the republic, the goals of science and scientific-innovative activity, the rights and responsibilities of subjects of scientific activity, mechanisms for financing science, stimulation of scientific achievements and the organizational and legal basis for their application, as well as the leading role and tasks of science in ensuring the political, economic, social and cultural development of the country, the growth of

well-being and the intellectual level of citizens, the acquisition of new knowledge by them, etc. This Law notes such principles, goals and priorities of state policy in the field of scientific activity as the integration of science into public life, transparency and accessibility of scientific results, ensuring integrative communication and dialectical unity in the relationships between science, education, economics and society, research the problems of forming based on knowledge of intellectual society and economics, etc. [6].

Museums play an exceptional role in solving all of the above issues, since, along with the collection, preservation, study and display of museum objects, one of the main areas of museum activity is education. In the modern period, when the information flow is constantly growing, society is in great need of information that reflects the truth, which is presented in a language it understands. Along with universities and research institutions, museums are indispensable sources of this information, which for many years have been collecting and displaying materials related to the experience of the evolution of society. Unlike academic institutions, museums are more accessible to the general public. Therefore, the possibilities of museums in the field of education are multifaceted; these cultural institutions are unique intermediaries between objects of historical and cultural heritage and subjects who accept cultural codes, that is, visitors [19, p. 3].

Museums operating in our country, to one degree or another perform the function of education. Naturally, large museums in Azerbaijan are most involved in this area. For many years, the National Museum of the History of Azerbaijan and the National Museum of Azerbaijani Literature named after Nizami Ganjavi functioned under the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences; they were not only temples of culture, but also scientific institutions of the republic, in which large-scale research was carried out and important scientific results were obtained. According to the relevant Decree of the head of state, these two museums were transferred under the authority of the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Azerbaijan, however, scientific activity continues here, museums implement numerous events aimed at integrating science and education, and thereby actively participate in educational work.

Other major museums in the country are the Azerbaijan National Museum of Art, the Azerbaijan National Carpet Museum, the Azerbaijan State Museum of Musical Culture, the Museum of Modern Art, etc. These museums, as well as museums of art, literature, music and other profiles located in the capital and regions, try to take part in public life, especially to cooperate with secondary schools and higher educational institutions. Naturally, there are a number of problems, to identify and find ways to solve which, appropriate monitoring must be carried out, and for further activities a unified concept must be developed. We talked about the need for monitoring about ten years ago [2].

Improving museum activities in accordance with emerging realities. The Covid-19 pandemic that began in 2020 has created new realities in all areas, including in museum activities. One of the features of the pandemic and post-pandemic era is the accelerated development of electronic services. On the official websites of our major museums, their pages on social

networks Facebook and Instagram, as well as on YouTube channel, virtual tours and lectures are posted, in most cases in several languages. However, during the course of our research, it turned out that many museums in the republic do not have official websites and pages in the Wikipedia encyclopedia, or they exist, but are not updated. The limitation or complete absence of virtual activities of museums has a negative impact on their recognition within the republic, not to mention the global space. Our museums must operate in accordance with the requirements of the technological era. This will lead to their popularization both among the local population and among tourists.

In addition, we consider it necessary to create new museums that meet the requirements of the time. For example, in various regions of our republic, which are distinguished by their rich cultural and natural heritage, it is imperative to create *ecomuseums and "green routes" (Greenways)*. Ecomuseums are initiatives whose goal is both the development of tourism and the solution of socio-economic and cultural problems of the local population. Ecomuseums are often established along national, regional or international green routes.

The question of the need to create eco-museums in Azerbaijan was raised back in 2011 [13, p. 51-52], and later we made a proposal to create the first eco-museum in the village of Khinalig, emphasizing that this process would lead to the organization of the necessary archaeological and ethnographic research in the region, building the infrastructure necessary for the convenience of the rural population and creating new jobs, that is, improving the well-being of the local community as a whole, and also talked about the prospects for creating similar museums in Ivanovka, Lahic, Sheki, Ilisu, Gakh and other regions [15; 4].

Naturally, it is impossible to cover all physical and geographical regions of Azerbaijan at one time. From this point of view, specialists involved in the relevant industries must determine the regions in which the creation of "green routes" will be most productive, and decide in which areas eco-museums should be created, taking into account such factors as the villages located on these routes, the number of population and the state of infrastructure. Considering the creative work in the Karabakh region and upcoming goals, we consider it appropriate to create several "green routes" and eco-museums in this region. As experts note, "the creative economy that will be formed in the Karabakh economic region is of great importance in providing employment, increasing the share of creative goods and services in exports, achieving long-term economic growth... The transition from culture to economy, the creation of cultural and creative sectors will lead to the development of tourism [8, p. 172].

For the development of cultural and educational tourism, we also consider it necessary to create *museums of the history of cities*. Speaking about museums of the history of specific cities, it should be noted that the main advantage of these institutions over other types of museums is that the subject of research of these museums is everything that surrounds them. Museums of the history of cities create an opportunity for people to get to know their hometowns more deeply and learn more about the history of their origins. These museums exhibit everything – photography, cinema, folklore, etc., various programs are being implemented

[10, p. 6]. Museums of the history of cities tell the story of urban culture, popularize the uniqueness of communities, and engage in activities aimed at the cultural development of the population.

Only two museums of the history of cities are known to function in Azerbaijan. These are museums of the history of Sumgait and Mingachevir – two cities created in the 60-s XX century. It is interesting that in the same years a similar museum was created in Shusha, but it functioned for a very short time.

To date, we have developed and presented to the public the primary concepts of the history museums of Baku [12; 3], Shusha [9] and Nakhchivan [14]. We hope that these initiatives will soon find their solution.

And we explore the role of museums in the integration of science and education through the activities of scientific and technical museums and children's museums.

Scientific and technical museums should carry out work aimed at both protecting, studying and promoting scientific heritage, and popularizing scientific knowledge, as well as engaging in environmental education and training of people. Researchers include museums of this profile as museums that document the process of historical development of science and technology, have monuments of science and technology in their collections, promote the history of the development of technology and scientific knowledge, and also implement public events aimed at popularizing scientific and technical knowledge [5, p. 40].

For years now, we have prepared the primary concept of the Museum of the History of Science, which was planned to be created at ANAS. We are taking certain measures to practically implement this initiative.

We have also developed and submitted to the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Azerbaijan a project for a Children's Museum-Center. About *children's museums* we are talking since 2011 [11]. Let us note that children's museums perform more of an educational function than an entertainment one. During the game, children receive the necessary knowledge and try to master the world and determine their place in this world. As the author of the project for the Children's Palace Museum in Russia, Alexander Zelenko, wrote, a children's museum "should serve the interests of young citizens in the same way as modern museums serve adults." The idea of creating a children's museum is a very important idea, since "with the help of such a museum we bring pearls of material culture to children precisely in those years when they are enthusiastically interested in the world around them". The Children's Museum is a new and experimental event. He must be as mobile as possible, must be ready for various changes [16, p. 168].

The creation of special museums for children in Azerbaijan is a very important and necessary task. We believe that such museums should be created, first of all, in the regions of the republic, since in the capital adult museums implement special programs for children, but in the regions this is almost not observed. We also note that the creation of children's museums will be an important step not only in the upbringing and education of children and the organization of cultural family leisure, but also in the opening of new jobs in

cities and regions (teachers, educators, hall supervisors, stage directors, decorators, psychologists, etc.).

Conclusions and offers. Considering all of the above, we can confidently say that the role of museums in the formation of a knowledge society and the knowledge economy that develops in parallel with it cannot be denied. Expanding the functions of museums, the active participation of these institutions in the life of modern societies, their direct participation in both the collection and creation of knowledge - all this creates ample opportunities for close contact between museums and creative industries.

Like other countries in the world, Azerbaijan has entered a post-oil period. Thus, the further development of the republic no longer depends on the exploitation of natural resources, but on the development of agriculture and the non-oil industry, science, technology, tourism and other areas. All of the areas we have listed are based in one way or another on knowledge. Therefore, the issues of communicating information about scientific achievements, the results of ongoing research and experiments to the general public are of great importance and relevance. Museums play an important role in this matter. From this point of view, it is necessary to study the current state of the country's museums, for which monitoring should be carried out, and also to develop a unified concept aimed at determining the prospects for the further development of museums. And the creation of eco-museums, museums of the history of cities, scientific and technical and children's museums will play a significant role in the development of a knowledge society.

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